

JAPAN'S TOURISM POTENTIAL AND REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN JAPAN

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Abstract. *Japan is one of the most developed countries in the world with a thousand-year history, unique culture and traditions. This country, known to the world as "Japan", is actually called "Nihon Koku". The name is official, used on money, documents and postage stamps and means "Land of the Rising Sun".*

Keywords: *economic factor, Nihon Koku, Historical factor, Cultural factor, Geographical location and climate, Innovations and modern technologies.*

Japan is a country located in the Far East region of Asia and consists of an archipelago located in the Pacific Ocean. The total area of the country is 377,976 square kilometers, and by this indicator it ranks 61st in the world. However, it is considered one of the densely populated countries, and as of 2023, the number is more than 125.4 million. In terms of population, Japan ranks 11th in the world.

Japan is a developed country in many ways, including manufacturing, social security, international trade, education, and technology. Among them, tourism is developing in several areas:

- health resort and recreation center;
- such subtypes as sports and health, including water and mountain tourism;
- beach;
- educational;
- pilgrimage tourism;
- business tourism and MICE.

It is known that Japan has traditionally been one of the most advanced destinations in the world. On average, 30-40 million tourists have visited this place over the past decade. When the task of developing the tourism industry in a certain country arises, Japan's tourism potential and its development experience are studied first among other alternative countries.

When studying the tourism potential of Japan, it is advisable to take into account the following main factors of its development:

1. Economic factor;
2. Historical factor;
3. Cultural factor;
4. Geographical location and climate.
5. Innovations and modern technologies.

Japan ranks fourth in the world in terms of GDP and 30th in the world in terms of GDP per capita. The Human Development Index is very high, and its population leads in life expectancy. Traditionally, especially in the 20th century, when new industrial countries did not appear, Japan, together with the United States and Europe, made up the top three most advanced countries in the world economy in terms of production share and industrialization level.

It is not without reason that its currency has the highest share among the currencies of the US dollar and the euro. Japan's financial markets are also considered one of the oldest developed financial centers. It is known that among the charts that today represent the prices of shares and other assets on stock exchanges, the so-called "Japanese candlesticks" were first introduced on Japanese rice markets. Even today, the uniqueness of the Japanese banking and financial system attracts the attention of many industry representatives and encourages them to make business trips to financial centers such as Tokyo and Osaka to adopt this experience.

The most notable event in the history of the Japanese economy was the "Japanese Miracle" of the 1950s-1970s. During this period, it will become a competitor to American and European companies in the global automotive and electronics industry. In particular, brands such as Toyota, Mitsubishi and Yamaha will become a serious competitor in market share to Ford Motors, General Motors and Chrysler, which have become almost the dominant three in the world, and not only in the world, but also in the United States, where the companies are residents. Japanese brands such as Sony, Toshiba, Honda, Nintendo have a global scale. Toyota Corporation - TMK, deserves special attention in the global industry. Its unique production model Kaizen, sometimes known as the Toyota Production System (TPS), is a unique model that only Japanese specialists can successfully implement. This shows that not only technological but also human capital has a unique aspect in the Japanese economy.

The economic factor is one of the important factors determining the tourism potential of Japan. This is explained by the fact that Japan first became the center of capitalist, and then labor migration. Also, business representatives, banking and finance specialists regularly organize business trips to the capital of the country Tokyo and other large cities. All this is facilitated by business tourism.

The above economic feature determines the development of MICE tourism in Japan. In Japan, the status of world MICE cities has been achieved by Tokyo, Osaka, Nagoya, Kyoto, Hiroshima, Chiba, Sapporo, Sendai, Yokohama, Kobe, Kitakyushu. Table 1 lists hotels and other tourist accommodations in them.

Table 1

Global MICE cities in Japan and the number of tourist buildings and rooms in them

City name	Number of buildings	Number of rooms
Osaka	1374	-
Sapporo	188	27,848
Sendai	208	35,561
Yokohama	97	18,479
Nagoya	196	30,118
Kyoto	550	27,753
Kobe	96	14,947
Hiroshima	147	11,490
Kitakyushu	114	8,221

It is no secret that along with many historical, natural and economic factors influencing the development of the Japanese tourism industry, regulatory factors regulated by the state have also played an important role. Indeed, back in the 19th century, the reforms known as the Meiji Restoration laid the foundation for the development of tourism by liberalizing the movement of

foreign travelers to Japan, as well as domestic travelers. This tradition has continued, and legal norms regulating tourism have been developed and regularly improved to this day.

Legal norms regulating the modern Japanese tourism industry are primarily reflected in laws. It is also included in the provisions of various state programs, events and organizations implementing them.

The "Basic Law on Tourism" of Japan is the basis for the formation of the country's modern regulatory framework in the field of tourism. This law was adopted in 1963 and is implemented by the Japan International Cooperation Agency, the Tourism Department, the Ministry of Transport and the Japan National Tourism Organization (JNTO). This law consists of seven chapters and 23 articles, the basic structure of which is as follows:

Chapter I. General Rules (Articles 1-5);

Chapter II. Promotion of International Tourism (Articles 6-8);

Chapter III. Protection of Tourists, Improvement of Tourist Facilities, etc. (Articles 9-15);

Chapter IV. Tourism-Related Administrative Agencies and Organizations (Articles 16-17);

Chapter V. Tourism Policy Authority (Articles 18-23).

In addition to this law, in 1963, the Japan International Cooperation Agency, the Tourism Department, the Ministry of Transport, and the Japan National Tourism Organization (JNTO) published a publication entitled "Laws and Regulations on the Tourism Industry", which included the first. It consists of the Tourism Basic Law, as well as the Tourism Policy Council, the Powers of the Ministry of Transport and Related Laws, the Law for the Promotion of the International Tourism Industry, the JNTO, the Travel Agency, the Guide Interpreter, Improving the comfort of international tourist hotels, Mortgage of tourism instruments on real estate, laws governing statistical surveys of the international tourism industry, immigration control powers, the National Parks Act, and the Act Concerning Special Measures for the Preservation of the Historic Environment in Ancient Capitals.

Speaking at a plenary session of the House of Representatives on January 31, 2003, Prime Minister Junichiro Koizumi announced the government's decision to formulate a tourism development program, which has become one of the top priorities of the Koizumi administration.

In Japan, serious attention has been paid to the hotel sector. Great changes have taken place in the country's hospitality sector under the "Visit Japan" program initiated by the government. Japan is a high-tech country, and accordingly, its tourism infrastructure is also at a high level. The hotel sector in Japan is represented by various types of accommodation: *hoteru*, *ryokan*, *minshuku*, *onsen* hotels, business hotels, capsule hotels, luxury hotels, youth hostels. The advantage of Japanese hotels is their national identity and the atmosphere of Japanese hospitality.

The Basic Law on Tourism of 1963 was reintroduced in December 2006 as the Basic Law for the Promotion of National Tourism by a bill passed by the House of Representatives and came into effect in January 2007. This law clearly defined tourism as one of the pillars of Japan's 21st century policy for the first time. In order to comprehensively but organized support the development of national tourism, the law stipulates that the government will submit a "National Tourism Development Plan".

The law also specifies the following priority areas of government policy: the formation of internationally competitive and highly attractive tourist destinations, the enhancement of the international competitiveness of the tourism industry, and the encouragement of individuals who

contribute to the development of tourism, the promotion of international tourism, and measures to promote tourism. it is necessary to create a favorable environment.

Japan adopted the UNESCO World Heritage Convention on June 30, 1992. Japan has more than twenty World Heritage tourist sites, and these tourist destinations are famous all over the world and attract millions of foreign tourists every year. The government has assured international tourism organizations of their preservation and is taking initiatives in this direction. The government has developed the necessary mechanisms and standards for the preservation and high-quality restoration of historical monuments listed by international organizations such as UNICEF, World Cultural Heritage, and other historical monuments in the country, and the measures are being implemented. The government allocates funds and subsidies for this purpose.

The structures and organizations responsible for the regulatory framework for tourism in Japan include, as stated earlier, ministries, organizations, local governments, bureaus, and agencies.

REFERENCES

1. <https://imrs.uz/files/publications/ru/16639.pdf>
2. https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yaponiyada_turizm
3. [Global MICE Cities | Why Japan | Japan. Meetings & Events \(japanmeetings.org\)](http://japanmeetings.org)
4. <https://lex.uz/docs/2608443>